

THE INTEGRATION OF DIGITAL PRESERVATION INTO SHAREPOINT ONLINE

David Clipsham

Preservica
United Kingdom
david.clipsham@preservica.com
0009-0006-2611-8877

Jonathan Tilbury

Preservica
UK
jonathan.tilbury@
preservica.com
0009-0004-0438-1952

Abstract – The embedding of Digital Preservation technology into popular commercial content management platforms has been a goal of the digital preservation community for many years. This paper describes how this has been achieved for SharePoint Online, delivering decades of preservation best practice to users who do not even know they are using preservation. The techniques, data structures and digital preservation workflows used can be extended to many other information platforms.

Submission Type – Poster

Keywords – Born Digital Content, Workflows, Microsoft 365, SharePoint

Conference Topics – Tūtaki – Encounter

I. INTRODUCTION (HEADING 1)

Microsoft 365, with SharePoint Online at its heart, is by many estimates the most popular information management platform in the world with over 2 million organisations using it [1]. Much of the information held in SharePoint is required for long term preservation, either for an extended fixed retention period or in perpetuity. With this in mind, Preservica has spent the last three years creating a solution to fully integrate Digital Preservation technology seamlessly into the SharePoint 365 environment.

This poster explores the approaches to integration considered, the designs selected and the challenges overcome. It describes the Information Object structure devised, the tools built around this to ensure long term accessibility and how Digital

Preservation complexity is hidden by the integration and automation of its functions within this highly popular information management system.

II. SHAREPOINT RECORD ELEMENTS

The poster will explore the essential elements of SharePoint Online and describe which parts of these are appropriate for preservation. This will include SharePoint Library, Lists and Sites and how retention management is managed using Microsoft Purview.

III. INTEGRATION MODELS

The poster will explore different approaches to digital preservation integration including

- Web crawling and archiving
- Extract-transfer-load (ETL)
- Browse and extract using a product API
- Automatic transfer of tagged material using a product API
- User interface plug in
- Search and render plug in

IV. SELECTED ARCHITECTURE

The poster will describe how the elements were selected and how they were built, including the challenges overcome. This will include user interface extensions, searching for tagged content, transfer processing using the OPEX and PAX protocol [3], feedback to SharePoint, search using the SharePoint

indexes and render within the SharePoint environment. This will include screen shots of the elements as they appear to the user.

V. INFORMATION OBJECT STRUCTURE

The poster will describe the elements of the multi-part Information Object including a JSON file for the database record, zero to many content files, and any required rich metadata files, and show how these can be recognized as a specific object [4]. It will show how all generally accepted Digital Preservation principles can be applied to this Information Object to ensure it is retained for use long into the future. [2]

VI. CONCLUSION

The integration of Digital Preservation into Microsoft 365 was a highly ambitious project which has delivered all the good practice devised by the preservation community over the last two decades seamlessly into a popular information management platform. Whilst we are still at the foothills of what is achievable, it has successfully shown that this is possible, can be done in a way that is highly usable, popular and trustworthy and offers a pattern that can be re-used for many other platforms.

services. He has worked as CEO, Product Manager and Head of Research.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Microsoft have been highly supportive partner through this project and have helped with many of the challenges described.

REFERENCES

- [1] How Many Businesses Use Microsoft 365 in 2024?, <https://www.onecloud.com.au/resources/how-many-businesses-use-microsoft-365-in-2024/>
- [2] J. O'Sullivan, R. Smith and A. Gairey, "A Pragmatic Application of PREMIS", iPres 2019, Amsterdam
- [3] R. Smith and J. Tilbury, "OPEX and PAX: A transfer format for digital preservation content", iPres 2024, Ghent
- [4] J. O'Sullivan, R. Smith and J. Tilbury, "Identifying of multi-part digital objects", iPres 2021, Beijing

AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

David Clipsham is the File Format Analyst at Preservica, supporting system users in overcoming their file format-related challenges. He previously worked at The National Archives (UK), where among many roles, he spear-headed PRONOM file format research for around 10 years.

Jonathan Tilbury has been working in Digital Preservation for 25 years and founded Preservica, provider of commercial preservation software and

